

Dirac Bra-ket Notation for Interpreting Regional Distribution of Pulmonary Ventilation-Perfusion

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ABSTRACT

Newly developing technologies of imaging have shown that the regional distribution of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion is formed from lobules of Miller in varying degrees of ventilation and perfusion. The theoretical study in this paper proposes using Dirac's bra-ket notation for describing the pulmonary ventilation-perfusion relations of the multiple inert-gas elimination technique (MIGET) based on the lobular lung model instead of the classical alveolar model. Bra-ket notation and the corresponding rules of calculation would provide a useful tool to solve the difficulties between pulmonary functional images and physiological measurements in normal or diseased lungs, and offer an important basis for applying quantum mechanics to pulmonary physiology.

Key Words: *pulmonary ventilation-perfusion relations, Dirac bra-ket notation, lobule of Miller, Bohmian quantum theory*

INTRODUCTION

From a historical point of view, one can identify three phases in the advance of knowledge for understanding ventilation-perfusion relations in the whole lung (West JB and Wagner PD, 1977). The first phase was the recognition that the gas exchange in any lung unit is determined not only by the ventilation or blood flow but also by the ratio of one to the other (Krogh A and Lindhard J, 1917). Shortly after this new understanding, Haldane recognized that ventilation-perfusion inequality could cause hypoxemia (Haldane JS, 1922). The second phase began in the late 1940s. Some researchers addressed the qualitative relationships between ventilation, blood flow, and gas exchange by graphical analysis of these relationships (Fenn WO, Rhan H, and Otis AB, 1946). The third phase began in the mid-1960s, when researchers introduced computer procedures to describe the oxygen and carbon-dioxide dissociation curves (Kelman GR, 1966, 1967; Olszowka AJ and Farhi LE, 1968). This stimulated the development of numerical techniques for describing the gas-exchange behavior of the distribution of ventilation-perfusion ratios (West JB, 1969). Shortly after, the multiple inert-gas elimination technique (MIGET) was introduced, which allowed distributions of ventilation-perfusion ratios to be recovered from normal subjects and patients with various types of lung disease (Wagner PD, Saltzman HA, and West JB, 1974; West JB, 1977). The mathematical approach could estimate the ventilation-perfusion ratios by linear least-squares regression with smoothing. A remarkable amount of information for understanding ventilation-perfusion relationships in the human lung can be derived from this method and have been described quantitatively with the MIGET model.

Since the beginning of the 21st century, new functional imaging techniques have markedly developed to show the distribution of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion as clear images. Functional images have advanced us to a new phase of knowledge on ventilation-perfusion relationships in the lung because the images suggest that the smoothing hypothesis of ventilation-perfusion ratios is incorrect. Reconstructed functional images in various human lungs have revealed that the unit of ventilation-perfusion ratios is not the alveolus but the secondary lobule of Miller, and that the lung is divided by clusters of lobules as patch-like regions with varying degrees of ventilation and perfusion (Musch G et al., 2002; Venegas JG et al., 2005). Therefore, it is now necessary to reconstruct the distributions of ventilation and perfusion in the lung by clusters of the secondary lobules.

In this paper, the author has introduced Dirac's bra-ket notation (1958) and the corresponding rules of calculation to describe the degree of ventilation or perfusion in the pulmonary lobule, and provides the theoretical basis for

interpreting the topographical distribution of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion using quantum field theory.

SATE VARIABLES IN THE LOBULAR VENTILATION AND PERFUSION

Fractal trees of bronchi and pulmonary arteries

Since the late 1980s, high-resolution computer tomography (HRCT) has been established as an indispensable tool demonstrating gross anatomy and accurately characterizing abnormal findings (Webb WR, Mueller NL, and Naidich DR, 2009). Pulmonary HRCT images have revealed the anatomical and functional importance of the secondary lobule of Miller, which refers to the smallest unit of lung structure margined by connective tissue septa. The secondary lobules of Miller are irregularly polyhedral in shape and vary in size, measuring from 1.0 to 2.5 cm in diameter in most locations.

The pulmonary lobe is composed of lobular polyhedrons, each of which is supplied by a single corresponding bronchiole and an accompanying arteriole of approximately 0.5 mm in internal diameter. During spontaneous breathing, these fractal trees functionally integrate many lobules to the whole lung through asynchronous contractions or relaxations in time of corresponding lobular bronchiole and arteriole (Min KY et al., 2012). That is, through the fractal trees of bronchi and arteries, ventilation and perfusion would be seen in the lobular polyhedrons as the rhythmic flows, respectively. (Fig. 1)

2.2 Introduction of Dirac's ket and bra vectors

If one could see a lobular unit, one would observe a series of rhythmic ventilations and perfusions. Regarding Dirac's notation of vectors (1958), a forward series of ventilations during the forward fractionated period of $t=n\cdot\tau$, where τ is a unit interval of time dependent on the observational system, may be expressed by a ket vector, for example $|\Psi\rangle = |0110 \cdots 101\rangle$ (n number sequences of 0 or 1). A forward series of perfusions during the forward fractionated observational period may also be defined by another ket vector, $|\Phi\rangle = |10111 \cdots 001\rangle$ (n number sequences of 0 or 1). Whenever one has a set of vectors in any mathematical theory, one can always set up a second set of vectors, which mathematicians call dual vectors. The new bra vectors or simply bras are introduced here, and one of the bras is denoted by the symbol $\langle |$ the mirror image of the symbol for a ket vector. Thus, a bra vector may be defined as a backward series of ventilations during the backward fractionated period of $t=n\cdot\tau$, where τ is a unit interval of time dependent on the observational system, for example $\langle\Psi| = \langle 0110 \cdots 100|$ (n number sequences of 0 or 1). A backward series of perfusions during the backward fractionated observational period may be also defined as another bra vector, $\langle\Phi| = \langle 1011 \cdots 001|$ (n number sequences of 0 or 1). (Fig. 2)

2 Superposition of vectors

Ket vectors may be multiplied by complex numbers and may be added together to give other ket vectors, e.g., from two ket vectors $|A\rangle$ and $|B\rangle$ we can form

$$c_1|A\rangle + c_2|B\rangle = |R\rangle \cdots (2.3.1)$$

where c_1 and c_2 are any two complex numbers. A ket vector, which is expressible linearly in terms of certain others, is said to be dependent on them. A set of ket vectors is called independent if none of the vectors is expressible linearly in terms of the others. An acceptable assumption is that each physiological state of a lobule at a particular time corresponds to a ket vector, the correspondence being such that if a physiological state results from the superposition of certain other states, its corresponding ket vector is expressible linearly in terms of the corresponding ket vectors of the other states, and conversely. Thus the state R results from a superposition of the states A and B when the corresponding ket vectors are connected by (2.3.1). The superposition relationship of (2.3.1) is symmetrical between all three states A, B, and R.

A further assumption must be introduced, namely the assumption that by superposing a state with itself cannot form

any new state, but only the original state over again. If the original state corresponds to the ket vector $|A\rangle$, when it is superposed with itself the resulting state will correspond to

$$c_1|A\rangle + c_2|A\rangle = (c_1 + c_2)|A\rangle \dots (2.3.2)$$

where c_1 and c_2 are numbers. Now one may have $c_1+c_2=0$, in which case the result of the superposition processes would be nothing at all, the two components having cancelled each other by an interference effect. No corresponding state to the zero ket vector exists. Apart from this special case, the resulting state must be the same as the original one, so that $(c_1+c_2)|A\rangle$ corresponds to the same state that $|A\rangle$ does. Thus, a state is specified by the direction of a ket vector, and any length one may assign to the ket vector is irrelevant. All states in ventilation or perfusion of the lobule are one-one correspondence with all the possible directions for a ket vector, no distinction being made between the directions of the ket vectors $|A\rangle$ and $-|A\rangle$.

1. RULES OF CALCULATION AMONG VECTORS

Scalar product

According to the mathematical concept of dual vectors, a scalar product of a bra vector $\langle A|$ and a ket vector $|B\rangle$ may be introduced as $\langle A|B\rangle$, i.e. as a juxtaposition of the symbols for the bra and ket vectors. One may look upon the symbols $\langle |$ and $| \rangle$ as a distinctive kind of brackets. A scalar product $\langle A|B\rangle$ now appears as a complete bracket expression and a bra vector $\langle A|$ or a ket vector $|B\rangle$ as an incomplete bracket expression. It is introduced as the rules that any complete bracket expression denotes a number, and any incomplete bracket expression denotes a vector, of the bra or ket kind according to whether it contains the first or second part of the bracket.

The calculation rules of a scalar product among $\langle A|$ and $|B\rangle$ may be expressed by symbolically by

$$\langle A| \{ |B\rangle + |B'\rangle \} = \langle A|B\rangle + \langle A|B'\rangle \dots (3.1.1)$$

$$\langle A| \{ c|B\rangle \} = c\langle A|B\rangle \dots (3.1.2)$$

c being any number. A vector is considered to be completely defined when its scalar product with every ket vector is given, so that if a bra vector has its scalar product with every ket vector vanishing, the bra vector itself must be considered as vanishing. In symbols, if

$$\langle A|B\rangle = 0, \quad \text{all } |B\rangle \quad \text{then } \langle A| = 0 \dots (3.1.3)$$

The sum of two bra vectors $\langle A|$ and $\langle A'|$ is defined by the condition that its scalar product with any ket vector $|B\rangle$ is the sum of the scalar products of $\langle A|$ and $\langle A'|$ with $|B\rangle$,

$$\{ \langle A| + \langle A'| \} |B\rangle = \langle A|B\rangle + \langle A'|B\rangle \dots (3.1.4)$$

The product of a bra vector $\langle A|$ and a number c is defined by the condition that its scalar product of $\langle A|$ with $|B\rangle$,

$$\{ c\langle A| \} |B\rangle = c\langle A|B\rangle \dots (3.1.5)$$

Equations (3.1.1) and (3.1.4) show that products of bra and ket vectors satisfy the distributive axiom of multiplication, and equations (3.1.2) and (3.1.5) show that multiplication by numerical factors satisfies the usual algebraic axioms. The bra vectors are quite different kinds of vectors from the kets, and so far there is no connection between them except for the existence of a scalar product of a bra and a ket.

Conjugate imaginary relations

Next, to introduce the assumption that there is a one-one correspondence between the bras and the kets, such that the bra corresponding to $|B\rangle + |B'\rangle$ is the sum of the bras corresponding to $|B\rangle$ and to $|B'\rangle$, and the bra corresponding to $c|B\rangle$ is \bar{c} times the bra corresponding to $|B\rangle$, i.e. $\langle B|\bar{c}$, \bar{c} being the conjugate complex number to c . Thus the bra corresponding to $|B\rangle$ will be written with $\langle B|$. The relationship between a ket vector and the corresponding bra makes it reasonable to call one of them the conjugate imaginary of the other.

On account of the one-one correspondence between bra vectors and ket vectors, any state of the lobule at a particular time may be specified by the direction of a bra vector just as well as by the direction of a ket vector. In fact, the whole theory will be symmetrical in its essentials. Given any two ket vectors $|A\rangle$ and $|B\rangle$, it is assumed that two numbers $\langle A|B\rangle$ and $\overline{\langle B|A\rangle}$ are always equal, i.e.,

$$\langle A|B\rangle = \overline{\langle B|A\rangle} \dots (3.2.1)$$

Putting $|B\rangle = |A\rangle$ here, the number $\langle A|A\rangle$ must be real, and $\langle A|A\rangle$ is assumed to be more than zero except $|A\rangle = 0$, i.e.,

$$\langle A|A\rangle > 0 \dots (3.2.2)$$

Linear operators

We may look upon two states $|A\rangle$ and $|F\rangle$ with the passage from $|A\rangle$ to $|F\rangle$. Introducing the symbol α for a linear operator, we may write $|F\rangle = \alpha|A\rangle$, in which the result of α operating on $|A\rangle$ is written like a product of α with $|A\rangle$. We make the rule that in such products the ket vector must always be put on the right of the linear operator. As the results, symbolically these equations may be obtained as,

$$\alpha\{|A\rangle + |A'\rangle\} = \alpha|A\rangle + \alpha|A'\rangle \dots (3.3.1a)$$

$$\alpha\{c|A\rangle\} = c\alpha|A\rangle \dots (3.3.1b)$$

A linear operator is considered to be completely defined when the result of its application to every ket is given.

Linear operators can be added together, the sum of two linear operators separately would produce. Thus, $\alpha + \beta$ is defined by

$$\{\alpha + \beta\}|A\rangle = \alpha|A\rangle + \beta|A\rangle \dots (3.3.2)$$

for any $|A\rangle$. Equations (3.3.2) and (3.3.1a and b) show that products of linear operators with ket vectors satisfy the distributive axiom of multiplication. Linear operators can also be multiplied together, the product of linear operators being defined as that the application of two operators successively. Thus, the product $\alpha\beta$ is defined as the linear operator which, operating on any ket $|A\rangle$, changes it into that ket which one would get by operating first on $|A\rangle$ with β , and then on the result of the first operation with α . In symbols,

$$\{\alpha\beta|A\rangle\} = \alpha\{\beta|A\rangle\} \dots (3.3.3)$$

This definition appears as the associative axiom of multiplication for the triple product of α , β , and $|A\rangle$, and allows us to write this triple product as $\alpha\beta|A\rangle$ without brackets. However, this triple product differs from the triple product of $\beta\alpha|A\rangle$, so that in general $\alpha\beta$ must differ from $\beta\alpha$. The commutative axiom of multiplication does not hold for linear operators.

In a special case two linear operators α and β are such that $\alpha\beta$ and $\beta\alpha$ are equal. In this case it is to say that α commutes with β , or that α and β commute. By repeated applications of these processes of adding and multiplying linear operators, one can form sums and products of more than two of them, and one can proceed to build up algebra with them. In this algebra the commutative axiom of multiplication does not hold, and also the product of operators may vanish without either factor vanishing. All the other axioms of ordinary algebra, including the associative and distributive axioms of multiplication, are valid.

So far we have considered linear operators operating only on ket vectors. We can give a meaning to their operating also on bra vectors, in the following way. Take the scalar product of any bra $\langle B|$ with the ket $\alpha|A\rangle$. This scalar product is a number which depends linearly on $|A\rangle$ and therefore, from the definition of bras, it may be considered as the scalar product of $|A\rangle$ with some bra. The bra thus defined depends linearly on $\langle B|$, so we may look upon it as the result of some linear operator applied to $\langle B|$. This linear operator is uniquely determined by the original operator α

and may be reasonably called the same linear operator operating on the bra vectors. A suitable notation to use for the resulting bra when α operates on the bra $\langle B|$ is $\langle B|\alpha$, as in this notation the equation which defines on $\langle B|\alpha$ is

$$\{\langle B|\alpha\}|A\rangle = \langle B|\{\alpha|A\rangle\} \dots (3.3.3)$$

for any $|A\rangle$, which simply expresses the associative axiom of multiplication for the triple product of $\langle B|$, α , and $|A\rangle$. We therefore make the general rule that in a product of a bra and a linear operator, the bra must always be put on the left. We can now write the triple product of $\langle B|$, α , and $|A\rangle$ simply as $\langle B|\alpha|A\rangle$ without brackets. It may easily verify that distributive axiom of multiplication holds for products of bras and linear operators just as well as for products of linear operators just as well as for products of linear operators and kets.

There is one further kind of product that has meaning in our scheme, namely, the product of a ket vector and a bra vector with the ket on the left, such as $|A\rangle\langle B|$. To examine this product, let us multiply it into an arbitrary ket $|P\rangle$, putting the ket on the right, and assume the associative axiom of multiplication. The product is then $|A\rangle\langle B|P\rangle$, which is another ket, namely, $|A\rangle$ multiplied by the number $\langle B|P\rangle$, and this ket depends linearly on the ket $|P\rangle$. Thus, $|A\rangle\langle B|$ appears as a linear operator that can operate on kets. It can also operate on bras, its product with a bra $\langle Q|$ on the left being $\langle Q|A\rangle\langle B|$, which is the number $\langle Q|A\rangle$ times the bra $\langle B|$. The product $|A\rangle\langle B|$ is to be sharply distinguished from the product $\langle B|A\rangle$ of the same factors in the reverse order, the later product being, of course, a number.

Conjugate relations

The linear operators are complex quantities since one can multiply them by complex numbers and get quantities of the same nature. Hence, they must correspond in general to complex physiological variables we can measure. Consider the ket which is the conjugate imaginary of $\langle P|\alpha$. This ket depends antilinearly on $\langle P|$ and depends linearly on $|P\rangle$. It may therefore be considered as the result of some linear operator operating on $|Q\rangle$. This linear operator is called the adjoint of α or $\bar{\alpha}$. With this notation, the conjugate imaginary of $\langle P|\alpha$ is $\bar{\alpha}|P\rangle$. In formula (3.2.1), put $\langle P|\alpha$ for $\langle A|$ and its conjugate imaginary $\bar{\alpha}|P\rangle$ for $|B\rangle$. The result is

$$\langle Q|\bar{\alpha}|P\rangle = \overline{\langle P|\alpha|Q\rangle} \dots (3.4.1)$$

This is a general formula holding for any ket vectors $|Q\rangle, |P\rangle$ and any linear operator α , and it expresses one of the most frequently used properties of the adjoint. Putting $\bar{\alpha}$ for α in (3.4.1), we get

$$\langle Q|\bar{\alpha}|P\rangle = \overline{\langle P|\bar{\alpha}|Q\rangle} = \langle Q|\alpha|P\rangle$$

by using (3.4.1) again with $|P\rangle$ and $|Q\rangle$ interchanged. This holds for any ket $|P\rangle$, so we can infer from (3.2.1),

$$\langle Q|\bar{\alpha} = \langle Q|\alpha$$

and since this holds for any bra vector $\langle Q|$, we can infer $\bar{\bar{\alpha}} = \alpha$. Thus, the adjoint of a adjoint of the linear operator is the original linear operator. It is reasonable to assume that the adjoint of a linear operator corresponds to the conjugate complex of a physiological variable. Thus, we may call the adjoint alternatively the conjugate complex linear operator, which confirms the notation $\bar{\alpha}$. A linear operator may equal its adjoint, and is then called self-adjoint. It corresponds to a real physiological variable, so it may be called alternatively a real linear operator. Any linear operator may be split up into a real part and a pure imaginary part. For this reason the words ‘conjugate complex’ are applicable to linear operators and not the words ‘conjugate imaginary’. The conjugate complex of the sum of two linear operators is obviously the sum of their conjugate complexes. To get the conjugate complex of the product of two linear operators α and β , $\langle A| = \langle P|\alpha$, $\langle B| = \langle Q|\beta$, so that $|A\rangle = \bar{\alpha}|P\rangle$, $|B\rangle = \beta|Q\rangle$. The result is

$$\langle Q|\bar{\beta}\bar{\alpha}|P\rangle = \overline{\langle P|\alpha\beta|Q\rangle} = \langle Q|\bar{\alpha}\bar{\beta}|P\rangle$$

Since this holds for any $|P\rangle$ and $\langle Q|$, it can be inferred that

$$\bar{\bar{\beta}}\bar{\bar{\alpha}} = \bar{\alpha}\bar{\beta} \dots (3.4.2)$$

Thus, the conjugate complex of the product of two linear operators equals the product of the conjugate complexes of the factors in the reverse order. As simple examples of this result, it should be noted that, if α and β are real, in general $\alpha\beta$ is not real. Only when α and β commute is $\alpha\beta$ itself also real. It is possible to get its conjugate complex by referring directly to the definition of the adjoint. Multiplying $|A\rangle\langle B|$ into a general bra $\langle P|$ as $\langle P|A\rangle\langle B|$, whose imaginary ket is $\overline{\langle P|A\rangle}\langle B| = \langle A|P\rangle\langle B| = |B\rangle\langle A|P\rangle$. Hence,

$$\overline{|A\rangle\langle B|} = |B\rangle\langle A| \quad \dots (3.4.3)$$

OBSERVABLES AND PROBABILITY

Eigen values and eigen vectors

The following equation is considered here,

$$\alpha|P\rangle = a|P\rangle \quad \dots (4.1.1)$$

where α is a linear operator and a is a number. This equation usually presents itself in the form that α is a known linear operator, and the number a and the ket $|P\rangle$ are unknowns, which we have to try to choose so as to satisfy, ignoring the trivial solution $|P\rangle = 0$. Equation (4.1.1) means that the linear operator α applied to the ket $|P\rangle$ just multiplies this ket $|P\rangle$ a numerical factor without changing its direction. This same α applied to other kets will in general change both their lengths and their directions. It should be noticed that only the direction of $|P\rangle$ is of importance in equation (4.1.1). It should be also considered as the conjugate imaginary form of equation as follows,

$$\langle Q|\beta = b\langle Q| \quad \dots (4.1.2)$$

where b is a number. Here the unknowns are the number b and the non-zero bra $\langle Q|$.

If (4.1.1) is satisfied, we shall call a an “eigenvalue” of the linear operator α , or of the corresponding physiological variable, and we shall call $|P\rangle$ an “eigenket” of the linear operator or physiological variable. Further, we shall say that the eigenket $|P\rangle$ belongs to the eigenvalue a . Similarly, if (4.1.2) is satisfied, we shall call b an eigenvalue of β and $\langle Q|$ an eigenbra belonging to this eigenvalue b .

If an eigenket of α is multiplied by any number not zero, the resulting ket is also an eigenket and belongs to the same eigenvalue as the original one. It is possible to have two or more independent eigenkets of a linear operator belonging to the same eigenvalue of that linear operator, e.g. (4.1.1) may have several solutions, $|P_1\rangle, |P_2\rangle, |P_3\rangle, \dots$, say, all holding for the same value of a , with the various eigenkets $|P_1\rangle, |P_2\rangle, |P_3\rangle, \dots$, independent. In this case it is evident that any linear combination of the eigenkets is other eigenkets belonging to the same eigenvalue of the linear operator, e.g.

$$c_1|P_1\rangle + c_2|P_2\rangle + c_3|P_3\rangle + \dots$$

is another solution of (4.1.1), where c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots are any numbers.

In the special case when the linear operator α of equation (4.1.1) and (4.1.2) is a number k , any ket $|P\rangle$ and bra $\langle Q|$ will satisfy these equations provided a and b equal k . Thus a number considered as a linear operator has just one eigenvalue, and any ket is an eigenket and any bra is an eigenbra, belonging to this eigenvalue. Putting for α the real linear operator ξ as follows,

$$\xi|P\rangle = a|P\rangle \quad \dots (4.1.3a)$$

$$\langle Q|\xi = b\langle Q| \quad \dots (4.1.3b)$$

Three results can be deduced as follows, 1) the eigenvalues are all real numbers, 2) the eigenvalues associated with eigenkets are the same as the eigenvalues associated with eigenbras, and 3) the conjugate imaginary of any eigenket is an eigenbra belonging to the same eigenvalue, and conversely. The third result makes it reasonable to call the state corresponding to any eigenket or to the conjugate imaginary bra an eigenstate of the real physiological variable ξ .

Observables

When we observe, we can measure some physiological variable. Physiologically the result of such a measurement must always be a real number. Then, if the physiological system is in an eigenstate of a real physiological variable ξ , belonging to the eigenvalue ξ' , then a measurement of ξ will certainly give as the result the number ξ' . Conversely, if the system is in a state such that a measurement of ξ is certain to give one particular result instead of giving one or other of several possible results according to a probability law, as is in a general case, then the state is an eigenstate of ξ , and the result of the measurement is the eigenvalue of ξ' to which this eigenstate belongs. These assumptions are reasonable on account of the eigenvalues of real linear operators always being real numbers. Some of the consequences of the assumptions will be noted.

If we have two or more eigenstates of a real physiological variable ξ belonging to the same eigenvalue ξ' , two eigenstates of ξ belonging to different eigenvalues are orthogonal. Thus, with the physiological system in any state, any result of a measurement of a real physiological variable is one of its eigenvalues. Conversely, every eigenvalue is a possible result of a measurement of the physiological variable for some state of the system, since it is certainly the result if the state is an eigenstate belonging to this eigenvalue.

If a certain real physiological variable is measured with the system in a particular state, the states into which the system may jump on account of the measurement are such that the original state is dependent on them. These states into which the system may jump are all eigenstates of ξ , and hence the original state is dependent on eigenstates of ξ . But the original states may be any state, so we can conclude that any state is dependent on eigenstates of ξ . If we define a complete set of states to be a set such that any state is dependent on them, then the conclusion can be formulated as the eigenstates of ξ form a complete set. A real physiological variable whose eigenstates form a complete set is called an observable. Thus any quantity that can be measured is an observable.

We make the general assumption that if the measurement of the observable ξ for the system in the state corresponding to $|x\rangle$ is made a large number of times, the average of all the results obtained will be $\langle x|\xi|x\rangle$, provided $|x\rangle$ is normalized. If $|x\rangle$ is not normalized, as is necessarily the case if the state x is an eigenstate of some observable belonging to an eigenstate in a range, the assumption becomes that the average result of a measurement of ξ is proportional to $\langle x|\xi|x\rangle$. This general assumption provides the basis for a general physiological interpretation of this method.

Probability

Let the observable be ξ and let the state correspond to the normalized ket $|x\rangle$. Then, the general assumption of observables tells us that not only the average value of ξ is $\langle x|\xi|x\rangle$, but also the average value of any function of ξ , $f(\xi)$ say, is $\langle x|f(\xi)|x\rangle$. Take $f(\xi)$ to be that function of ξ which is equal to unity when $\xi = c$, c being some real number, and zero otherwise, or $f(\xi) = \delta_{\xi c}$ ($\delta_{\xi c} = 0$ when $\xi \neq c$, $\delta_{\xi c} = 1$ when $\xi = c$). The average value of this function of ξ is just the probability, P_c say, of ξ having the value of c as follows,

$$P_c = \langle x|\delta_{\xi c}|x\rangle \dots (4.3.1)$$

If c is not an eigenvalue of ξ , $\delta_{\xi c} (= 0)$ multiplied into any ket of ξ is zero, and $P_c = 0$. The probability of ξ having a value within small range, say from c to $c+dc$, which we may call $P(c)dc$, is equal to the average value of that function of ξ which is equal to unity for ξ lying within the range c to $c+dc$ and zero otherwise. This function of ξ has a meaning according to an observable. Denoting it by $\chi(\xi)$, we have

$$P(c) dc = \langle x|\chi(\xi)|x\rangle \dots (4.3.2)$$

If the range c to $c+dc$ does not include any eigenvalues of ξ , we have as above $\chi(\xi) = 0$ and $P(c) = 0$. If $|x\rangle$ is not normalized, the right-hand sides of (4.3.1) and (4.3.2) will still be proportional to the probability of ξ having value c

and lying within the range c and $c+dc$, respectively.

4.4 Commutability of observables

A state may simultaneously be an eigenstate of two observables. If the state corresponds to the ket vector $|A\rangle$ and the observables are ξ and η , we should then have the equations, $\xi|A\rangle = \xi'|A\rangle$ and $\eta|A\rangle = \eta'|A\rangle$, where ξ' and η' are eigenvalues of ξ and η respectively. We can now deduce $\xi\eta|A\rangle = \xi\eta'|A\rangle = \xi'\eta|A\rangle = \xi'\eta|A\rangle = \eta\xi|A\rangle$, or $(\xi\eta - \eta\xi)|A\rangle = 0$. This suggests that the chances for the existence of a simultaneous eigenstate are most favorable if $\xi\eta - \eta\xi = 0$ and the two observables commute. If they do commute, so many simultaneous eigenstates exist that they form a complete set. Conversely, if ξ and η are two observables such that their simultaneous eigenstates form a complete set, the ξ and η commute. The idea of simultaneous eigenstates may be extended to more than two observables.

If certain observables commute, states exist for which they all have particular values in the sense of simultaneous eigenstates. Thus, one can give a meaning to several commuting observables having values at the same time. For any state one can give a meaning to the probability of particular results being obtained for simultaneous measurements of several commuting observables. In general, one cannot observe a system in a definite state without disturbing that state and spoiling it for the purposes of a second observation. One cannot then give any meaning to two simultaneously made observations. Although in a special case when the two observables commute, the observations are considered as non-interfering or compatible, in such a way that one can give a meaning to the two observations being simultaneously made and can discuss the probability of any particular results being obtained. The two observations may, in fact, be considered as a single observation of a more complicated type, the result of which is expressible by two numbers instead of a single number. Any two or more commuting observables may be counted as a single observable, the result of a measurement that consists of two or more numbers. The states for which this measurement is certain to lead to one particular result are the simultaneous eigenstates.

2. LOBULAR VENTILATION AND PERFUSION

Creation and annihilation operators

To describe states of a pulmonary lobule in ventilation and perfusion as shown in Fig.2, two linear operators are introduced, i.e., the creation operator $\bar{\alpha}_\ell$ and the annihilation operator α_m (two operators have a conjugate relation) as follows,

$$\bar{\alpha}_\ell|0\rangle = \bar{\alpha}_\ell|\hat{0}00 \cdots 0 \hat{0}^{\ell}00\rangle = |\hat{0}00 \cdots 0 \hat{1}^{\ell}00\rangle$$

$$\alpha_m|\hat{0}00 \cdots 0 \hat{1}^m00\rangle = |\hat{0}00 \cdots 0 \hat{0}^m00\rangle = |0\rangle$$

where $|0\rangle$ is the state of empty state (no ventilation or no perfusion) in the lobule, and $\hat{0}$ means the starting time of observation. The creation operator can insert ventilation or perfusion into the lobule one observes for measurement at the fractionated ℓ -th time interval. The annihilation operator can annihilate ventilation or perfusion from the lobule one observe for measurement at the fractionated m -th time interval. Thus,

$$\alpha_m \bar{\alpha}_\ell |0\rangle = \alpha_m |\hat{0}00 \cdots 0 \hat{1}^{\ell}00 \cdots 0\rangle \cdots (5.1.1)$$

When $\ell = m$ is, (5.1.1) becomes $|0\rangle$, i.e.

$$\alpha_m \bar{\alpha}_m |0\rangle = |0\rangle \cdots (5.1.2)$$

When $\ell \neq m$ is, the state disappears, i.e.

$$\alpha_m \bar{\alpha}_\ell |0\rangle = 0 \cdots (5.1.3)$$

It is important to note that the linear operator $\bar{\alpha}_\ell \alpha_m$ always annihilate the state, i.e.

$$\bar{\alpha}_\ell \alpha_m |0\rangle = \bar{\alpha}_\ell (\alpha_m |0\rangle) = 0 \dots (5.1.4)$$

Thus, $\alpha_m \bar{\alpha}_\ell$ does not commute, i.e. $\alpha_m \bar{\alpha}_\ell \neq \bar{\alpha}_\ell \alpha_m$.

Any state of ventilation or perfusion in a lobule can be constructed by the multiplying of creation-annihilation operators to the initial empty state $|0\rangle$ according to the superposing rule as follows,

$$\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} c_\ell \bar{\alpha}_\ell |0\rangle = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} c_\ell |000 \dots 0 \overset{\ell}{\hat{1}} 00 \dots 0\rangle \dots (5.1.5)$$

where each c_ℓ is a number ($\ell = 0,1,2,3, \dots$), and $\bar{\Psi}$ is a linear operator.

Observation and the rule of probability

When one can observe ventilation or perfusion in the corresponding lobule with the state of $\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle$ at the s-th fraction of time during the fractionated observational period ($s = 0,1,2,3 \dots, n$), one may describe ventilation or perfusion in the lobule by noting observable (1) or not-observable (0). Repeated observation may provide the frequency ratio of ventilation or perfusion as $r_s = f_s/M_s$, where f_s is the frequency of ventilation or perfusion observed in the lobule at the s-th fraction of time, and M_s is the total frequency of measurements. (Fig.3) If the M becomes larger, r_s may reach the probability of P'_s as a limit value. This is an assumption as the probability rule in this study, i.e.,

$$P'_s \equiv \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f_s}{M} = \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f_s}{\sum_{s'} f_{s'}} \propto \bar{c}_s c_s = |c_s|^2 \dots (5.2.1)$$

When the probability is normalized as P_s as follows,

$$\sum_s P_s = \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_s f_s}{\sum_{s'} f_{s'}} = 1$$

this normalized probability P_s is obtained by the following,

$$P_s = \frac{P'_s}{\sum_{s'} P'_{s'}} = \frac{\bar{c}_s c_s}{\sum_{s'} \bar{c}_{s'} c_{s'}}$$

The bra vector $\langle 0|\Psi$ is obtained as corresponding to anti-linearly the ket vector of state $\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle$. The product of the bra and ket $\langle 0|\Psi\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle$ is expressed as follows,

$$\langle 0|\Psi\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle = \sum_s \bar{c}_s c_s = \sum_s |c_s|^2$$

When the product $\langle 0|\Psi\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle$ is normalized by $\langle 0|\Psi\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle = \sum_s |c_s|^2 = 1$, the normalized probability is expressed by the equation,

$$P_s = |c_s|^2 \dots (5.2.2)$$

3. PULMONARY VENTILATION-PERFUSION RELATIOSHIPS

3.1 Measurements in functional images of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion

Recent progress in technology making pulmonary functional images has shown the topographical distribution of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion in spontaneous human breathing on the architectural basis of the lobular structure of the lung. Thus, we may quantitatively assess clusters of lobules with various degree of ventilation or perfusion. Now let the measurement/observation system be defined by the linear operator \hat{O} . According to Musch et al. (2002) the measuring method of topographical distributions of ventilation and perfusion in the human lung was a bolus infusion of $^{13}\text{N}_2$ during a short apnea and measuring the concentration of $^{13}\text{N}_2$ during apnea \hat{O}_q and the ensuing period of $^{13}\text{N}_2$ washout \hat{O}_v . Thus, pulmonary ventilation or perfusion was separately observable in a cluster of lobules. Each lobule was assessed having some average ventilation or perfusion by time constant of regional dynamics of $^{13}\text{N}_2$

concentration. Based on the expression of Dirac in this study, the average value of ventilation ($\langle v \rangle$) or perfusion ($\langle q \rangle$) in the lobule with the state $\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle$ can be assessed with measurement system \hat{O}^v or \hat{O}^q as follows,

$$\langle v \rangle = \frac{\langle 0|\Psi\hat{O}^v\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle}{\langle 0|\Psi\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle} \dots (6.1.1a)$$

$$\langle q \rangle = \frac{\langle 0|\Psi\hat{O}^q\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle}{\langle 0|\Psi\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle} \dots (6.1.1b)$$

These equations mean that the physiological state of the lobule determines the average value of measurements. The cluster of lobules with the same average value is recognizable as the same physiological state. That is, the cluster would be a statistical ensemble of lobules with the same physiological state. Thus, the physiological state of cluster $\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle$ may be described by the following,

$$\bar{\Psi}|0\rangle = c_0|0\rangle + c_1|1\rangle \dots (6.1.2)$$

$$|c_0|^2 + |c_1|^2 = 1 \dots (6.1.3)$$

where c_0 and c_1 are numbers.

3.2 Ket vectors for pulmonary ventilation-perfusion

Since the ventilation-perfusion state of a lobule should be characterized by combination of simultaneous corresponding ventilation and perfusion, it should be described by the double ket vectors for corresponding ventilation and perfusion as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi\rangle|\Phi\rangle &= |0100 \dots 101101\rangle|1000 \dots 011101\rangle = a|0\rangle|0\rangle + b|0\rangle|1\rangle + c|1\rangle|0\rangle + d|1\rangle|1\rangle \\ &= |\Psi, \Phi\rangle = a|0,0\rangle + b|0,1\rangle + c|1,0\rangle + d|1,1\rangle \dots (6.2.1) \end{aligned}$$

where a, b, c and d are numbers. The four ket vectors $|0,0\rangle, |0,1\rangle, |1,0\rangle$, and $|1,1\rangle$ are a complete orthogonal set. When it is possible to directly observe these states of ventilation and perfusion by some measurement system, the state of $|0,0\rangle$ would be observed by the probability as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle 0,0|\Psi, \Phi\rangle^2 &= \langle 0,0|(a|0,0\rangle + b|0,1\rangle + c|1,0\rangle + d|1,1\rangle)\rangle^2 \\ &= \langle 0,0|a|0,0\rangle + \langle 0,0|b|0,1\rangle + \langle 0,0|c|1,0\rangle + \langle 0,0|d|1,1\rangle\rangle^2 = |a|^2 \end{aligned}$$

, and other states are also observed by the probabilities by $\langle 0,1|\Psi, \Phi\rangle^2 = |b|^2$, $\langle 1,0|\Psi, \Phi\rangle^2 = |c|^2$, or $\langle 1,1|\Psi, \Phi\rangle^2 = |d|^2$. The normalization of probability is expressed by the following,

$$|a|^2 + |b|^2 + |c|^2 + |d|^2 = 1 \dots (6.2.2)$$

Another complete orthogonal set of states can be also defined as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi +\rangle &= \frac{|0,0\rangle + |1,1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |\pi -\rangle = \frac{|0,0\rangle - |1,1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \\ |\sigma +\rangle &= \frac{|0,1\rangle + |1,0\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |\sigma -\rangle = \frac{|0,1\rangle - |1,0\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned}$$

The state vector $|\Psi, \Phi\rangle$ can also be described by the superposition of these vectors as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi, \Phi\rangle &= a|0,0\rangle + b|0,1\rangle + c|1,0\rangle + d|1,1\rangle \\ &= \frac{a+d}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{|0,0\rangle + |1,1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) + \frac{b+c}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{|0,1\rangle + |1,0\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) + \frac{b-c}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{|0,1\rangle - |1,0\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) + \frac{a-d}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{|0,0\rangle - |1,1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \\ &= a'|\pi +\rangle + b'|\sigma +\rangle + c'|\sigma -\rangle + d'|\pi -\rangle = (a'|\pi +\rangle + d'|\pi -\rangle) + (b'|\sigma +\rangle + c'|\sigma -\rangle) \dots (6.2.3) \end{aligned}$$

The vectors $(a'|\pi +\rangle + d'|\pi -\rangle)$ and $(b'|\sigma +\rangle + c'|\sigma -\rangle)$ express the coupled ventilation-perfusion state and the uncoupled state in the lobule, respectively, and also the numbers obey the following normalized relation,

$$|a'|^2 + |b'|^2 + |c'|^2 + |d'|^2 = 1 \dots (6.2.4)$$

Superposed summation of every lobular state would define the pulmonary ventilation-perfusion state of the whole lung $|\Psi, \Phi\rangle_P$ as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi, \Phi\rangle_P &= \sum_{j=1}^N |\Psi, \Phi\rangle_j = \left(\sum_{j=1}^N a'_j \right) |\pi +\rangle + \left(\sum_{j=1}^N b'_j \right) |\sigma +\rangle + \left(\sum_{j=1}^N c'_j \right) |\sigma -\rangle + \left(\sum_{j=1}^N d'_j \right) |\pi +\rangle \\ &= A' |\pi +\rangle + B' |\sigma +\rangle + C' |\sigma -\rangle + D' |\pi +\rangle \dots (6.2.5) \end{aligned}$$

where A' , B' , C' , and D' are numbers, and the following relation may exist,

$$|A'|^2 + |B'|^2 + |C'|^2 + |D'|^2 = 1 \dots (6.2.6)$$

Thus, the pulmonary ventilation-perfusion relation should be divided conceptually into the four functional compartments.

3.3 MIGET method

The multiple inert-gas elimination technique (MIGET) has been developed as a means of estimating the \dot{V}_A/Q distribution. The principle of MIGET is the following: If an inert gas is dissolved in 5% dextrose or normal saline and then infused at a constant rate into a peripheral vein, a steady state of gas exchange across the lung is reached within a few minutes. In any single unit in the lung, the relationships among the alveolar (P_A), end-capillary (P_c), and mixed venous (P_v) partial pressure is given by the following equation,

$$\frac{P_A}{P_v} = \frac{P_c}{P_v} = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + \dot{V}_A/\dot{Q}} \dots (6.3.1)$$

In this expression, \dot{V}_A/\dot{Q} is the value of the ventilation-perfusion ratio of the lung single unit in question and λ is the blood gas partition coefficient of the gas being infused. This expression is derived from simple mass balance considerations on the assumption of (a) a steady state of gas exchange in the lungs, (b) continuous ventilator and circulatory movement of gas and blood through the lungs, and (c) alveolar-end-capillary diffusion equilibration of partial pressure for the gas, well argued on the theoretical and experimental grounds.

The single unit of the lung for ventilation-perfusion is assumed to be described by (6.3.1) and the results summed to represent total lung gas-exchange. We have as a result for excretion (E) and retention (R) as follows,

$$E \equiv \frac{P_{\text{EXP}}}{P_v} = \sum_{j=1}^N \dot{V}_{A_j} \cdot \left[\frac{\lambda}{\lambda + (\dot{V}_A/\dot{Q})_j} \right] \dots (6.3.2)$$

$$R \equiv \frac{P_{\text{art}}}{P_v} = \sum_{j=1}^N \dot{Q}_j \cdot \left[\frac{\lambda}{\lambda + (\dot{V}_A/\dot{Q})_j} \right] \dots (6.3.3)$$

Here, P_{EXP} is mixed expired and P_{art} is mixed arterial inert gas partial pressure, and \dot{V}_{A_j} and \dot{Q}_j are, respectively, fractional alveolar ventilation and blood flow of the j -th single unit, of which there are N in the entire lung. The variables R , E , and λ can all be measured experimentally during a steady state produced by a continuous inert gas infusion described above. Because $\dot{V}_{A_j} = \dot{Q}_j \cdot \dot{V}_A/\dot{Q}_j \cdot (\dot{Q}_T/\dot{V}_{ET})$ where \dot{Q}_T and \dot{V}_{ET} are total lung blood flow and ventilation, respectively, the equations (6.3.2) and (6.3.3) are actually not independent and reflect the same variable \dot{V}_A/\dot{Q} views from opposite sides of the blood-gas barrier. The relationship, unit by unit, between \dot{V}_A , \dot{Q} , and \dot{V}_A/\dot{Q} can be determined mathematically from measurements of R , E , λ , \dot{Q}_T , and \dot{V}_{ET} .

Several approaches to using the retention and excretion data have been tried. West JB and Wagner PD (1977) have demonstrated graphically beautiful distributions of ventilation and perfusion using the standard computer software for

50-compartment model with enforced smoothing. This is too complex to apply in clinical settings, and there has been no theoretical reason for how many compartments are sufficient to describe the pulmonary ventilation-perfusion relationship. According to the model of (6.2.5), four compartments should be necessary and sufficient to define the pulmonary ventilation-perfusion relationship. Recently, Rees and colleagues (2006) have showed that a simple four-compartment model provides a good description of lung pathology following oleic acid infusion in pigs.

3.4 Interpreting functional images using Dirac's notation

Quantitative imaging technologies have been developing to make up the actual regional distributions of ventilation and perfusion in animals and humans. These technologies are now able to directly estimate the regional ventilation and perfusion quantitatively as clusters regarding degrees in density of indicator agents. Since the density of indicator agents in the regional cluster may correspond to the average ventilation or perfusion in the regional area, the lobules with same density of indicator agents are considered to be an ensemble of lobules with the same physiological state according to (6.1.1a) and (6.1.1b). Thus, each lobule in the statistical ensemble of states $|\Psi, \Phi\rangle$ has its own ventilation and perfusion as follows,

$$\langle \dot{V}_A \rangle = \langle \Psi, \Phi | \hat{O}^v | \Psi, \Phi \rangle \dots (6.4.1a)$$

$$\langle \dot{Q} \rangle = \langle \Psi, \Phi | \hat{O}^q | \Psi, \Phi \rangle \dots (6.4.1b)$$

$$\dot{V}_A / \dot{Q} = \frac{\langle \dot{V}_A \rangle}{\langle \dot{Q} \rangle} \dots (6.4.2)$$

where \hat{O}^v and \hat{O}^q are operators of the measurement system for ventilation and perfusion, respectively. Then, the distribution in number of lobules would be recognizable according to the ventilation-perfusion ratio of (6.4.2) through measuring the functional images. The distributions of \dot{V}_A / \dot{Q} in the functional image would be applicable to interpret gas exchange in the lung by using MIGET equations of (6.3.2) and (6.3.3).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Dirac's bra-ket notation and Shroedinger's wave equation

Recent innovative development of imaging technologies including HRCT and MRI have provided many clear images on regional distributions of physiological function in the lung. Two basic problems have emerged as difficulties to explain in classical physiological concepts and assumptions: 1) the functional lung unit is not an alveolus but a secondary lobule of Miller, and 2) the regional distributions of pulmonary function are not changing smoothly along the whole lung but are fractionated by clusters of lobules. This study aims to propose another way to describe the regional distributions of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion without classical assumptions.

The conditions of ventilation and perfusion in the lobule are characterized by the rhythmic patterns in both air and blood flows in the lobule through rhythmic contractions of smooth muscle in the lobular bronchioles and arterioles dependent on respiratory and cardiac rhythmic motions during the period of observation. For these rhythmic physiological phenomena, the author applied Dirac's bra-ket notation, composed of angle brackets and vertical bars shown as section 5.1, for expressing the rhythmic patterns of state variables in the lobule. The ket vector expresses the state of rhythmic flows defined by a usual forward series of zero-one variables. The bra vector is also the defined dual vector indicating a backward series of zero-one variables from a mathematical viewpoint. According to Dirac's notation, the inner product (or dot product on a complex vector space) of two vectors is denoted by $\langle \phi | \psi \rangle$, consisting of a left part, $\langle \phi |$ called the bra, and a right part, $|\psi \rangle$ called the ket. The overlap expression $\langle \phi | \psi \rangle$ is typically interpreted as the probability for the physiological state ϕ to change into the physiological state ψ as shown in section

4.3. An acceptable assumption is that the steady physiological state is defined by $\langle \psi | \psi \rangle = 1$. These expressions would be applicable to any rhythmic physiological phenomena.

This notation has been designed to facilitate the formal manipulation of linear-algebraic expressions. For example, a linear operator is a map that inputs a ket and outputs a ket. That is, if \hat{O} is a linear operator and $|\psi\rangle$ is a ket, then $\hat{O}|\psi\rangle$ is another ket. Then, operators can also be viewed as acting on bras from the right hand side. Specifically, if \hat{O} is a linear operator and $\langle \psi |$ is a bra, then $\langle \psi | \hat{O}$ is another bra defined by the rule of (3.3.3) as follows ($\langle \psi | \hat{O} | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi | (\hat{O} | \psi \rangle) = \langle \psi | \hat{O} | \psi \rangle$). This expression gives the expectation value, or average value, of the observable represented by operator \hat{O} for the system in the physiological state $|\psi\rangle$. The linear operator is able to extend to describe dynamic changes in the physiological system.

Dirac's bra-ket notation for physiological states in a linear space is a way of representing a state in a linear space in a way that is free of the choice of coordinate but allows us to easily insert a particular choice of coordinates and to conveniently convert from one choice of coordinates to another. When the inner product of two physiological states is interpreted as the probability of transition between them, Dirac's notation would help us substantially in thinking about describing complex distributions of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion through manipulating symbolic representations.

When the physiological state of a lobule is expressed by a ket vector $|\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle$ at the time t , and at the time t' ($t' > t$), the state is also expressed by another ket vector $|\Psi(t'), \Phi(t')\rangle$. A linear operator proceeding the time $\hat{U}(t'; t)$ is introduced for expressing the transition of state from $|\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle$ to $|\Psi(t'), \Phi(t')\rangle$

$$|\Psi(t'), \Phi(t')\rangle = \hat{U}(t'; t) |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle \dots (7.1.1)$$

If it is at $t'=t$,

$$\hat{U}(t'; t) = \hat{U}(t; t) = 1 \text{ or } \hat{U}(t; t) |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle = |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle \dots (7.1.2)$$

In addition, if $t'' > t' > t$, the state $|\Psi(t''), \Phi(t'')\rangle$ is also expressed by the following equation as

$$|\Psi(t''), \Phi(t'')\rangle = \hat{U}(t''; t') |\Psi(t'), \Phi(t')\rangle = \hat{U}(t''; t') \{ \hat{U}(t'; t) |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle \}$$

Then, the following relation is obtained as a new rule of connection,

$$\hat{U}(t''; t) = \hat{U}(t''; t') \hat{U}(t'; t) \dots (7.1.3)$$

Let us consider the transitional change in the state from $|\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle$ to $|\Psi(t + \Delta t), \Phi(t + \Delta t)\rangle$ by the infinitesimal change in time Δt as follows,

$$|\Psi(t + \Delta t), \Phi(t + \Delta t)\rangle = \hat{U}(t + \Delta t; t) |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle \dots (7.1.4)$$

From combining (7.1.1) and (7.1.4), the following equation is obtained on the basis of (7.1.2),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{|\Psi(t + \Delta t), \Phi(t + \Delta t)\rangle - |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle}{\Delta t} &= \frac{\hat{U}(t + \Delta t; t) |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle - |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle}{\Delta t} \\ &= \left[\frac{\hat{U}(t + \Delta t; t) - \hat{U}(t; t)}{\Delta t} \right] |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle \dots (7.1.5) \end{aligned}$$

Based on the rule of connection (7.1.3), it is possible to let Δt toward zero as follows,

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\hat{U}(t + \Delta t; t) - \hat{U}(t; t)}{\Delta t} \right] = \left[\frac{d}{dt'} \hat{U}(t'; t) \right]_{t'=t} \dots (7.1.6)$$

In the simplest case of a time-independent operator, the following equation is introduced,

$$\left[\frac{d}{dt'} \hat{U}(t'; t) \right]_{t'=t} = c \hat{H} \dots (7.1.7)$$

where c is a number and \hat{H} is a time-independent linear operator called as the Hamiltonian. Thus, the dynamics in transition of physiological states is expressed by the motion equation as follows,

$$\frac{d}{dt} |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle = c \hat{H} |\Psi(t), \Phi(t)\rangle \dots (7.1.8)$$

This is a corresponding Shroedinger's wave equation in quantum mechanics.

4.2 Quantum theory and pulmonary ventilation-perfusion

In the recently published book, "What is the biological variability?" (Min K, 2014), the author proposed that physiological variables be described by a Bohmian model of quantum mechanics (Bohm D and Hiley BJ, 1993) from the stochastic optimal control theory because many cells in physiological systems would take their common optimal criterion together as an appropriate level of organized living processes. The organized living processes would be enfolded with every region of the physiological system including cells rather than being localized. According to the Bohmian model of quantum theory (Bohm D and Hiley BJ, 1993), this enfolded order in the physiological system would be embodied in the form of Hamiltonian of (7.1.8).

Regional distributions of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion are formed as dynamic but steady repeatable physiological processes dependent upon two central mechanisms; the first is respiratory and cardiac rhythmic motions, and the second is rhythmic motions of smooth muscles in the bronchioles and the arterioles. How these rhythmic motions determine the distributions of pulmonary ventilation and perfusion is very important for clinical intervention strategies for patients with cardiopulmonary failure. The author has proposed a theoretical model named Fractal Phasic Perfusion (FPP), which describes the relationship between the distribution of pulmonary perfusion and the physiological parameters of cardiac motion (Min K, 2014). Recently developing technologies have provided clear and quantitative images of topographical distributions of ventilation and perfusion. Thus, new pulmonary functional images will provide a significant amount of topographical data for statistical analysis, from which we will be able to find an appropriate form of Hamiltonian using Dirac's ket-bra notation. To find the form of Hamiltonian would provide deeper insight in rationally understanding pulmonary ventilation and perfusion.

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Legend for figures

Fig. 1 A lobular lattice from a lobe of lung

The lobe of lung consists of many lobules, each of which is supplied with ventilation and perfusion through asynchronous motions of bronchioles and arterioles.

Fig. 2 Describing physiological states in ventilation and perfusion with Dirac's bra and ket vector notation through the introduction of creation and annihilation operators

Two linear operators are introduced, i.e., the creation operator $\overline{\alpha}_\ell$ and the annihilation operator α_m (two operators have a conjugate relation).

Fig. 3 Rules of Probability

Repeated observations may provide the frequency ratio of ventilation or perfusion as $r_s = f_s/M_s$, where f_s is the frequency of ventilation or perfusion observed in the lobule at the s-th fraction of time, and M_s is the total frequency of measurements.

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig3.

Observation

